

Global BPO Market size reaches \$400 Billion, Where Bangladesh stand?

The idea of Outsourcing came from American glossary “outside resourcing” is also known as Business Process Outsourcing (BPO). The process of hiring another individual or company, either domestically or internationally, to handle business activities for you. It has become a common business practice that allows small and medium-sized businesses to reduce certain costs like non-core business expenses, high-taxes, labor cost and strong govt regulations.

There has so many popular category to most freelancers or outsourcing providers in to following – Inbound Customer Service, Outbound Telemarketing, Web Design & Development, SEO & Online Marketing, Back Office/Admin Support, Virtual Assistant services, Accounting and HR Management, Marketing and Sales Support.

In Asia as well as globally India and the Philippines have both been popular destination for BPO by global companies. Our neighbor country India crosses 100 billion dollar, Philippines \$25b, Vietnam \$5b, Pakistan \$2b and Sri Lanka has reached \$1b in recent year whereas Bangladesh stand behind less than a billion dollar, its \$600m. I think, South Asian countries has the most potential to create strong network of delivery chain and the decrease of expert skill in Europe as well as US’s increasingly debt will force both in to long term economic crisis, this is perfect time for the Asia’s to capture the market in due time.

Gartner: Global Outsourcing Market Size, 2011-2015 (\$B)

Notes:

Source: © Gartner, Inc. Forecast: IT Services, 2008-2015, 2Q11 Update. June 16, 2011.

AO - Application Outsourcing, IO - Infrastructure Outsourcing

Bangladesh is the 44th largest market-based economy. Goldman's Sachs has included Bangladesh in Next Eleven after BRIC. According to the IMF, Bangladesh's economy is the second fastest growing major economy of 2016 of 7.1%. In recent year, Bangladesh has been recognized by a US company AT Kearney a leading Management consultancy firm as the 26th best destination for IT outsourcing.

Bangladesh is constantly growing and drawing global attention of the developed countries to outsource their IT & ITES products and hiring hundreds thousands of freelancers by using online works marketplace like Upwork, Freelancers, Fiverr and Bangladeshi only local marketplace Belancer. Approximately 60,000-80,000 Freelancers registered and working on different marketplace and already secured top ten position in different skill category.

Chief Architect of Digital Bangladesh Mr. Sajeeb Wajed along with ICT Division and It's Youngest Minister Mr. Zuanid Ahmed Palak targeted to reach \$5 billion outsourcing revenue by 2021. In recent year so many summits, events, program Like Digital World with BASIS, and BPO Summit with BACCO happened throughout the country to create massive awareness to connect young people to make Bangladesh is the next IT destination and convert labor intensive economy to knowledge intensive economy to celebrate Golden Jubilee of Bangladesh. There has so many milestone has completed and tremendous progress so far including TAX exemption till 2024 for IT and ITES companies, Internet backbone and bandwidth cost reduced from 27,000 to 625 Taka/MBPS in last eight years, more than 2000 Sheikh Russell Digital Lab has established nationally and 12 Software Park is on the way to established. Govt has taken special scheme under Skill & Employment program to train and employ about 2 million young people.

There has some major challenges to flourish BPO industry in Bangladesh, according to Gartner main obstacle are infrastructure, language skill, data and IP rights. There is need some obvious step to reach vision 2021-

Power: There has so many step has taken still it's require more to meet national demands

Infrastructure: Nationwide Broadband connectivity and High Speed Internet is backbone of BPO.

Skill: There has huge gap between industry and academia our socio-culture too much depending on academic creativity rather than intellectual creativity. Good News, Govt has taken huge step for job skill & employ under popular scheme i.e SEIP, LICT and LEDP.

Language: In the age of globalization and as fastest growing economy we can't just avoid international language since most of our target clients are English spoken.

Research: Bangladesh ICT industry require depth down industry research to determine demands and supply gap as well decide upon solid data source.

Roadmap: Govt has included ICT on 7th of 5th year planning first time but now its' require an long term milestone based execution plan to implement on time also track the progress with all stake holder.

Synergy: ICT Division has already taken significant and required step to create beautiful synergy between trade associations BASIS, BACCO, ISPAB, E-Cab to work and meet vision 2021.

Awareness: ICT Division has taken lead to create the awareness of ICT is our future and spread to root level.

Brand Bangladesh: Alike Philippines for Call Center destination, Sri Lanka for Accounting, Bangladesh needs to work hard into create an global signature and identity in couple of skill or industry destination like Marketing or Designs whereas millions of people will works.

National Skill Database: It is important to have skill database to understand and determine the demand and supply.

Marketplace: International online works freelancing marketplace size is \$4.6 billion in different skill category on Upwork, Freealancers Fiverr and others. Our only local marketplace belancer.com has delivered \$ 0.35 Million after one year of it's launched. Now we've to collect huge works from global market.

Product Driver Creative Economy: Bangladesh should work on to develop their own products.

National IT Capacity: In order to develop own capacity of Bangladeshi skill workers, govt should subsidy or supporting packages who will work on products or software developments.

Women at Work: There has significant ratio dropped out women at education and work, we can include millions of educated women on outsourcing work.

Access To Finance: There is no better Financial packages or facility or access for the IT or ITES companies to start or grow, that should be address immediately to solve.

Local Market: our local market average size is more than 160 million dollar which is also helpful to develop our own eco-system.

The Government has declared IT as a thrust sector, tremendous activity is going on in every sector including e-commerce, e-governance, computer networking, Internet, web browsing, web applications, multimedia product development etc. Some active steps and initiatives are already there, as described above for an exposure of the present and future prospects of IT & ITES outsourcing in Bangladesh.

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